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To cite this article: J Bleeg *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2767** 042026

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The impact of blockage and wakes on seven power performance tests conducted at two wind farms

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Abstract. Blockage and wakes can potentially influence wind turbine power performance measurements (PPM), distorting the measured power curve relative to the true performance of the test turbine. In this study, we take a previously proposed method to correct for the impact of blockage and wakes and test it on seven PPM conducted in simple terrain at two wind farms. Each PPM was completed according to the prevailing standard from the International Electrotechnical Commission. The correction factors derive from Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes simulations of the two wind farms, and we apply these factors to the measured wind speed data on a record-by-record basis. The wind speed corrections clearly reduce variability in the measured power coefficients for the three PPM affected by long-distance wakes. The corrections do not reduce performance variability within the other four PPM. They also do not reduce differences in measured performance between the turbines at each wind farm, though numerical site calibrations do. Given these results, and considering uncertainty in the measurements, including confounding influences like terrain and turbine differences, validation against many more PPM is likely needed to adequately assess the reliability and utility of the correction method.

1. Introduction

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standard for wind turbine power performance testing is designed to mitigate, and preferably avoid, any effect of turbine wakes or blockage on measured power curves [1]. Related requirements restrict the wind speed measurements to locations between two and four rotor diameters (D) upstream of the test turbine—close enough for the wind speed to be well correlated with conditions at the rotor, but far enough to largely avoid the influence of induction from the test turbine. To avoid the influence of wakes, the standard limits the valid wind direction sector so that any upstream turbine is at least $20 D$ away from the test. The IEC clearly states the purpose of these restrictions [1]: “The WME (wind measurement equipment) shall not be influenced by the wind turbine under test. The wind turbine under test and the WME shall not be influenced by neighboring operating wind turbines.” Evidence from the field, however, indicates that, despite these constraints and the intent behind them, turbine-related flow distortions still influence IEC-standard power performance measurements (PPM) [2]–[5].

Most PPM are conducted on the upstream perimeter of a wind farm, where wakes can usually be avoided—blockage effects, however, cannot. Offshore lidar measurements reported in [2] and [3] indicate that induction of the test turbine can influence the wind speed at typical PPM measurement locations. According to an analysis of anemometer data from three onshore wind farms, blockage effects arising from all the wind farm turbines (i.e. wind farm blockage) can also influence the

measured wind speeds—as well as, very likely, the wind speeds experienced by the test turbine [4]. Finally, an analysis of power performance measurements conducted in a row of five turbines, showed that blockage can affect the wind speed at the power performance mast to a different degree than the wind speed at the rotor, changing the power efficiency relative to what would be measured if the test turbine were operating in isolation [5].

The IEC standard includes procedures for assessing and correcting for terrain-related distortions in the wind field, but not turbine-related distortions. Given the evidence cited above, procedures to assess and correct for turbine-related distortions to the flow may also be needed.

Building upon an approach first outlined in Section 5.6 of [4], Bleeg in [6] presents a method to correct for the distorting influence of blockage on PPM. Sebastiani et al. explore and expand upon this formulation in [7], with added consideration of wake effects, nacelle-mounted lidar, and the possibility of making corrections based on measurements rather than modeling. They also test the correction method on simulated PPM at a notional wind farm. The results demonstrate the potential of the method to reduce uncertainty and bias in PPM. The current contribution tests the correction methodology on real-world PPM, specifically seven PPM across two operating wind farms, all conducted according to the IEC standard. The main objective is to assess the reliability and utility of the corrections.

2. Power performance measurements

The two wind farms selected for this study are located onshore, well inland, on simple terrain. At Wind Farm A, PPM were conducted on four turbines using one mast and one vertical lidar. All four corresponded to the same turbine model with a rotor diameter (D) of approximately 120 m. At Wind Farm B, the PPM were conducted on three turbines, all the same model, with $D \approx 150$ m. A single mast was used for the three PPM.

3. Numerical simulations

We simulated the PPM using a steady-state RANS model customized for wind farm flows [4]. The Boussinesq approximation is used to capture buoyancy effects. The turbulence model is standard $k-\epsilon$ with modified coefficients. And the wind turbines are represented with actuator disks where the body forces are functions of the average axial-component of velocity across the disk. These functions derive as described in [4] from manufacturer-issued theoretical (MIT) power and C_T curves. Mesh spacing is no greater than $1/10 D$ within $15 D$ of the wind farm and $1/20 D$ within $0.7 D$ of each rotor hub.

We ran the simulations in 20° wind direction increments at Wind Farm A and 2.5° increments at Wind Farm B, where the horizontal wind speed gradients are much stronger. The simulated directions cover the full test sectors; the simulated wind speeds range between 5.5 and 8.5 m/s at the WME locations. We simulated two stability classes at each wind farm, one corresponding to stable surface conditions and the other corresponding to unstable conditions. Potential temperature profiles prescribed at the inflow boundaries define the static stability, and a buoyancy production term in the closure equations represent the effect of the stratification on turbulence [8], which in turn influences the vertical profiles of velocity. For simulations of the unstable boundary layer, the inflow potential temperature profile is constant/neutral through the boundary layer with an adiabatic condition at the ground. To compensate for the absence of resolved convections, the model of the unstable boundary layer includes an additional buoyancy production term based on the similarity theory proposed in [9]. Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model simulations run over the PPM periods informed the inflow boundary conditions used in the microscale RANS simulations. The WRF boundary layer scheme is Mellor-Yamada-Janjic, and the minimum horizontal spacing is 3 km. For each set of WRF-derived inflow conditions, we ran three types of RANS simulations: freestream (no wind turbines), isolated (one test turbine), and wind farm (all turbines).

From the three types of simulations, we derive the correction factors described in the next section and organize them by test turbine, wind direction, and surface stability. The correction factors are then applied to the time series of measured wind speed using a look-up table, with the inputs being

measured wind direction and time of day. Time of day is used as a proxy for surface stability—data recorded between sunrise and sunset are labeled unstable, and records taken between sunset and sunrise are assumed to be stable.

4. Correction method

The target output of the correction method is a freestream power curve. A freestream power curve represents the power production of the turbine operating in isolation as a function of freestream wind speed, which is the wind speed at the turbine location absent the presence of the turbine. This definition/target comports with how power curves are used in energy yield analyses [7].

A power curve measured according to the IEC standard is not the same as a freestream power curve due to the influence of neighboring turbines as well as induction from the test turbine. The method to convert a measured curve to a freestream power curve can be thought of as a two-step process [7]:

- Correct to the power curve that would be measured if the test took place with the turbine operating in isolation, removing the influence of wind farm blockage and wakes
- Correct for the remaining influence of isolated turbine induction on the measured wind speed

The correction method described in [7] only affects the measured wind speed, not the power. The corrections can be applied to the wind speed column of the measured power curve, after binning and averaging the measured data, or they can be applied to each record in the measured wind speed data. We take the latter approach in this paper. The correction equations are as follows [7]:

$$U_m^I = U_m^{WF} \left(\frac{U_{disk}}{U_m} \right)^{WF} \left(\frac{U_m}{U_{disk}} \right)^I \quad (1)$$

$$U_m^\infty = U_m^I \left(\frac{U_m^\infty}{U_m^I} \right) \quad (2)$$

U is wind speed. The superscripts denote the turbine scenario: WF stands for wind farm (all turbines operating); I stands for isolated (the test turbine is operating in isolation and producing the same amount of power as in the test); and ∞ refers to freestream conditions (no turbines). The subscripts relate to location. The m subscript refers to where the wind speed is measured. The $disk$ subscript refers to conditions at the rotor disk face, with U_{disk} considered a power-equivalent wind speed (e.g. if $U_{disk}^I = U_{disk}^{WF}$, then $P^I = P^{WF}$, where P is power). Consistent with how the body forces are applied in the RANS model, U_{disk} in this study is equal to the mean of the axial-component of velocity across the disk.

The measured wind speed, U_m^{WF} , is first converted to what would be measured if the test turbine were producing the same amount of power while operating in isolation, U_m^I . In other words, Eq. 1 corrects for the influence of neighboring turbines on the measured power curve. Eq. 2 corrects for the remaining influence of induction from the test turbine, yielding U_m^∞ , the freestream wind speed that would prevail if the test turbine were operating in isolation and producing the same amount of power as in the actual test. The derivation of these equations can be found in [7].

The $(U_{disk}/U_m)^{WF}$ and $(U_m/U_{disk})^I$ values are extracted from the wind farm and isolated turbine simulations, respectively. The (U_m^∞/U_m^I) values come from a combination of the freestream and isolated simulations, which are run back-to-back with the same mesh and boundary conditions. We call this ratio the induction correction, or the Eq. 2 correction. Likewise, the product of the ratios $(U_{disk}/U_m)^{WF}$ and $(U_m/U_{disk})^I$ is referred to as the Eq. 1 correction. The total correction is the product of all three ratios, i.e. the product of the Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 corrections.

5. Site calibration

Terrain effects can cause the freestream wind speed at the WME to deviate from the freestream wind speed at the turbine location—which would affect the measured power curve. Recognizing this, the IEC standard requires an assessment of the terrain to determine whether the elevation variation exceeds prescribed limits. If a limit is exceeded, the standard further requires a site calibration, where the wind speed is measured at the two locations before turbine construction to establish ratios of freestream wind speeds by wind direction. These ratios are applied to the wind speeds measured during the ensuing PPM. The correction approach for turbine-related flow distortions described in the preceding section recovers the freestream wind speed at the location of the wind speed measurement, not the location of the turbine. To recover the freestream wind speed at the turbine location, the site calibration ratio must also be applied:

$$U_{\infty} = U_m^{\infty} \left(\frac{U}{U_m} \right)^{\infty} \quad (3)$$

The elevation variation near the seven PPM did not exceed any of the limits that would trigger a site calibration, and no site calibration was performed. However, according to the RANS results, the wind speed ratios $(U/U_m)^{\infty}$ can materially depart from 1.0 (Table 1). Thus, some of the results reported in the next section include applied numerical site calibrations.

Table 1: RANS-based numerical site calibration factors averaged over each test sector

	A1	A2	A3	A4	B1	B2	B3
Stable	1.031	1.025	1.003	0.990	0.998	1.010	1.021
Unstable	1.012	1.009	1.003	0.998	0.996	1.004	1.009

(Throughout this paper, “corrections” refer to wind speed adjustments made to account for turbine-induced flow distortions. “Site calibration” refers to wind speed adjustments related to terrain-induced flow distortions.)

6. Results and discussion

This section presents the results from the RANS-based analyses of PPMs at wind farms A and B. We first discuss Wind Farm B, where the derived corrections are substantial, making it more straightforward to connect them with specific physical phenomena and the geometry of the PPM. We then discuss Wind Farm A, where the corrections are less pronounced. Lastly, we consider how the results relate to the IEC standard for power performance measurements.

At each wind farm we simulate the same set of nominal wind directions for stable conditions and unstable conditions. These nominal wind directions correspond to 90 m above ground level at the inflow boundary. The simulated wind directions can be slightly different at the test locations.

6.1. Wind Farm B

The three test turbines at Wind Farm B are B1, B2, and B3. Figure 1 shows their locations relative to the PPM mast and some of the other turbines in the wind farm. The distances between the test turbines and the mast are 2.9, 2.1, and 3.3 rotor diameters, respectively. Figure 1 also shows the RANS-predicted hub-height wind speed relative to freestream conditions. According to the RANS results, wakes from a cluster of five turbines upstream of the test area affect the wind conditions experienced by the test turbines and mast. These upstream turbines are located just beyond the IEC-mandated 20 D minimum distance from the test, a requirement set to avoid the influence of upstream wakes. However, to the degree that the simulated wakes are consistent with reality, wakes from this five-turbine upstream cluster are likely to affect the measured power curves.

Figure 2 shows the correction factors derived from the RANS results using equations 1 and 2. The corrections are sensitive to wind direction and stability class and deviate substantially from 1.0. Comparing Figure 1 and Figure 2c helps illustrate how the Eq. 1 correction works. The mast is close to the center of the cluster wake when the wind direction is 281° while B3 is closer to the wake edge, where wind speeds are higher. This wake effect therefore influences the relationship between the measured wind speed and the power generated at B3. In other words, it affects the measured power curve. Equation 1 corrects for this effect, adjusting the measured wind speed upwards at 281° to be consistent with the wind speed we would expect to measure when the turbine is operating in isolation and producing the same amount of power. With a wind direction change of just 10° , to 291° , the opposite trend is evident: the test turbine B3 is more waked than the mast, and so the Eq. 1 correction decreases the wind speed for this wind direction (Figure 2c).

The Eq. 2 corrections vary much less with wind direction. They range between 1.005 and 1.023, depending primarily on stability class and the location of the mast relative to the test turbine location and test sector.

Figure 1: RANS-predicted percent change in wind speed relative to freestream at hub height during stable surface conditions at Wind Farm B with test turbines B1, B2, and B3. The wind direction is 281° at 'x', the PPM mast location.

If the correction factors are to be believed, the measured efficiency of the B1 turbine should be much higher when the wind direction is on the high side of the valid sector as compared to the low side. The opposite trend should be evident at B3. This is, in fact, what we see in the uncorrected power performance measurements.

The measured performance is very sensitive to wind direction, especially during stable conditions and particularly for turbines B1 and B3, as demonstrated in Figure 3a-c. This variability with wind direction reflects instances where the test turbine is more waked than the mast and vice-versa. These differences in wake exposure are not as dramatic for the B2 PPM because the mast is more directly upstream of B2 for wind directions within the test sector; indeed, performance variability with direction is less pronounced for B2 compared with the other two turbines. The RANS-derived corrections shown in Figure 2 significantly reduce the direction variability for all three turbines as shown in Figure 3d. The corrections also consistently reduce the standard deviation of C_p between 6 and 8 m/s within the full test sectors: by 16% for B1, 14% for B2, and 19% for B3.

Note that the raw correction factors are not applied directly to the wind speed data; Gaumond filtering [10] is applied to the corrections first. The raw correction factors, which come directly from the steady-state RANS results, do not account for wind direction variations that occur on the scale of minutes and kilometers. This variability can affect the power performance measurements, which are

recorded as 10-minute means. For example, when the wind direction is 281° , the sharp difference in wind speed between the mast and B3 evident in the steady-state RANS results (Figure 1 and Figure 2c) may be blunted in the field if the background wind direction, and in turn the trajectory of the wake, varies significantly during a 10-minute record with the same mean wind direction (281°). Gaumond filtering applied to the model results is designed to account for this real effect.

In this study, we calculated the Gaumond filtered corrections in 1° increments. For each measured record, the correction factor is interpolated from the resulting curves.

A key input to the Gaumond filtering is σ_a , which represents the local wind direction variability. In the absence of established guidelines for setting σ_a , we used the mean of the wind direction standard deviations from the filtered 10-minute records. The σ_a values set for B1, B2, and B3 are 4.5° , 4.5° , and 6.0° for stable conditions (night) and 6.3° , 6.5° , and 7.5° for unstable conditions (day). These values have the virtue of being determined objectively, but it is not clear whether wind vane standard deviations accurately represent wind direction variability for the time scales of interest. It is important that the σ_a values are accurate when the raw corrections vary sharply with wind direction because Gaumond filtering can have a substantial effect on curves with sharp variations as seen in Figure 2. Thus, uncertainty in σ_a is a source of uncertainty in the application of the correction factors to measurements at Wind Farm B.

Figure 2: RANS-predicted correction factors for turbines B1 (a), B2 (b), and B3 (c). The vertical magenta lines represent the bounds of the test sectors.

Although the Gaumond-filtered correction factors significantly reduce performance differences with wind direction for each wind turbine, the gaps do not fully close (Figure 3d). These remaining

gaps could be related to error in the RANS simulations and/or the correction methodology, but they also could relate to error in the Gaumond filtering. If, for example, we reduced the σ_a values, which are difficult to reliably estimate, the performance gaps with wind direction would decrease.

Wakes and blockage may also cause differences in the measured performance *between* the turbines (Figure 4, left). Applying the blockage- and wake-related corrections, however, does not appear to reduce these differences (Figure 4, middle). Some of the variability in measured performance between the turbines may relate to the lack of a site calibration. A numerical site calibration derived from the freestream RANS results applied on top of the wake and blockage corrections reduces the difference in performance between the turbines (Figure 4, right).

Figure 3: Mean measured power coefficient (C_p) between 6 m/s and 8 m/s at Wind Farm B: (a) unstable/day; (b) stable/night; (c) all data (no stability filter); and (d) all data corrected.

The test sector for each turbine is split into two direction sectors.

Figure 4: C_p for the three test turbines at Wind Farm B, averaged over the test sectors and between 6 m/s and 8 m/s. Three types of C_p are plotted: uncorrected (left), corrected (middle), and corrected with numerical site calibration (right). The dashed line represents the C_p from the MIT power curve.

6.2. Wind Farm A

The four test turbines at Wind Farm A are A1, A2, A3, and A4. Figure 5 shows their locations relative to the wind speed measurement locations. The distance between the upstream mast and turbines A1 and A2 is $2.9 D$; the distance between the upstream ground-based lidar and turbines A3 and A4 is $3.0 D$. Figure 5 also shows the RANS-predicted hub-height wind speed relative to freestream for one of the simulated wind directions. Turbine-scale and wind-farm-scale blockage effects are evident in the results, effects that could potentially influence the PPM. Wake effects, however, are not expected to significantly influence the PPM, as there are no upstream turbines within the test sectors. (Exception: Near the upper edge of the A2 test sector, there are three turbines $30+ D$ upstream of the PPM mast.)

Figure 5: RANS-predicted percent change in wind speed relative to freestream at hub height during stable surface conditions at Wind Farm A with focus on the four test turbines, A1 and A2 in (a) and A3 and A4 in (b). The wind direction is 286° at the mast and lidar, 'x' in (a) and (b), respectively.

Figure 6 shows the correction factors derived from the RANS results. The corrections related to induction of the test turbine (Eq. 2) are typically just over 1.01 during stable conditions and just under 1.005 during unstable conditions. The corrections related to the influence of the other wind farm turbines (Eq. 1) vary more with wind direction, especially during stable conditions. As at Wind Farm B, this variation in the Eq. 1 corrections largely determines the variation in the total corrections. That said, the blockage-influenced correction factors at Wind Farm A are generally much closer to 1.0 and vary much less with wind direction compared with the primarily wake-influenced correction factors at Wind Farm B. As a direct result, the impact of Gaumond filtering is much smaller at Wind Farm A despite using comparable σ_a levels (average of 4.2° for stable conditions and 8.4° for unstable).

When these Gaumond-filtered total correction factors are applied to the wind speed data records at Wind Farm A, the impact on the performance variation within each PPM is small. The standard deviation of measured C_p decreases only 0.3-1.1% across the four turbines. For example, the standard deviation of C_p for turbine A1 drops from 0.0735 to 0.0727, a negligible change.

The impact of the corrections on the mean performance of each turbine is more discernible. Figure 7 shows the mean measured C_p for each turbine for wind speeds between 6 m/s and 8 m/s. The C_p levels range between 0.459 and 0.479 (Figure 7, left). The blockage-related corrections decrease the C_p levels to between 0.446 and 0.467, but do not reduce the variation in performance between the turbines (Figure 7, middle). When the numerical site calibrations are applied, the C_p for three of the four turbines collapses to 0.45, but the C_p for A1 is an outlier at 0.424 (Figure 7, right). We do not have an explanation for this remaining difference. It is possible that turbine A1 is simply underperforming relative to the other turbines. After all, A1 has a lower C_p than A2 with or without the corrections and/or site calibrations, despite sharing the same PPM mast. It is also possible,

however, that the corrections, numerical site calibrations, and the modeling behind them are not representing the flow distortions caused by the turbines and/or the terrain with sufficient accuracy. There are several sources of uncertainty in a power performance analysis, with the overall uncertainty on the order of the corrections being applied. Thus, an assessment of the reliability of the corrections would benefit from validation at many more wind farms.

Figure 6: RANS-predicted correction factors for turbines A1 (a), A2 (b), A3 (c), and A4 (d). The vertical magenta lines represent the bounds of the test sectors.

Figure 7: Mean C_p for the four test turbines at Wind Farm A, between 6 m/s and 8 m/s and over the full test sectors. Three types of C_p are plotted: uncorrected (left), corrected (middle), and corrected with numerical site calibration (right). The dashed line represents the C_p from the MIT power curve.

6.3. Results considered relative to the IEC standard

In this section we discuss how the results compare with some key assumptions in the IEC standard. These assumptions relate to long-distance wakes, turbine effects in general, and terrain effects.

The IEC standard effectively assumes that wakes from turbines more than 20 D upstream of the test will not influence the test result. Measurements and simulations at Wind Farm B, however, show that wakes from turbines located just over 20 D upstream can have a large impact on the measured performance, especially during stable conditions. Admittedly, Wind Farm B represents an uncommon situation; PPMs more typically take place on the upstream perimeter of a wind farm, where the flow is usually wake free. That said, as more wind farms are built near to each other, wake-affected PPMs are likely to become more common.

More generally, The IEC standard effectively assumes that the correction factor for wake and blockage effects is always equal to 1.0. The results herein, however, indicate that the corrections can deviate quite a bit from 1.0. Even if the uncertainty prescription in the standard accounts for some of the related performance variation, an uncorrected bias may remain. For each one of the 7 PPMs analyzed in this study, the net impact of the RANS-based corrections reduces the calculated C_p .

Terrain effects may also be a source of bias. When the local terrain is simple and does not exceed limits that would trigger a measured site calibration, the IEC standard assumes the site calibration factor is equal to 1.0. Expected deviations from 1.0 are handled with a prescribed uncertainty, but again, a bias may remain. Because energy production is one of the most important considerations when placing wind turbines, the mean freestream wind speed at a given turbine location will exceed the mean wind speed at a location 2-4 D upstream more often than the other way around. In other words, the average site calibration factor, were it to be measured, is more likely to be greater than 1.0 than less. This is indeed what is seen in complex terrain as demonstrated with actual site calibrations. It may also be true in simpler terrain: for 5 of the 7 PPMs in this study, the numerical site calibration factors exceed 1.0 on average, raising U_∞ above U_m^∞ and reducing C_p .

7. Conclusions

A method to correct for the influence of blockage and wakes on power performance measurements was tested on seven IEC-standard PPM. At Wind Farm B the corrections clearly reduce the strong sensitivity of the observed power performance to wind direction. Wakes from a cluster of five turbines located just over 20 D from the PPM are very likely the main cause of these performance sensitivities. The corrections also reduce the variability of C_p within the 6 to 8 m/s bin, the only bin evaluated. At Wind Farm A, where the PPM are not subject to wakes, the corrections do not materially reduce the performance variation within the 6 to 8 m/s bin. The corrections also do not reduce the variation in performance between turbines at either wind farm, though the numerical site calibration factors do.

The lack of a consistent reduction in performance variability across the two wind farms could be an indication of shortcomings in the correction approach and/or the flow model. However, they could also relate to uncertainty in the PPM, including confounding influences such as terrain and differences between the test turbines (e.g. if a turbine had a persistent yaw or pitch misalignment). Validation against more PPMs is needed to better understand the reliability and utility of the corrections.

8. Financial support

This research is supported by the EU-funded project FLOW under Grant Agreement ID 101084205.

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